

CONTROLLED IMPACT TESTS ON WOVEN-FABRIC/EPOXY RESIN CFRP PANELS WITH AND WITHOUT ADDITIONAL CARBON NANOTUBE REINFORCEMENT

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SUMMARY

Plain woven CFRP carbon/epoxy specimens, with and without additional carbon nanotube reinforcement, have been impacted in controlled-impact tests and sectioned subsequently for microstructural investigation. The results suggest that the panels with additional CNT reinforcement have a significantly greater ability to resist impact damage than specimens without CNT reinforcement.

Keywords: Impact test, CNTs

INTRODUCTION

Recently, nanoscale materials have attracted much attention as dispersed phases for the improvement of the mechanical and physical properties of polymer matrices. This attention has significantly increased with the detection of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in 1991 by Iijima [1]. The mechanical properties of CNTs, which include a high Young's modulus and high strength [2-3], in combination with electrical properties and a nanometric size (diameter $d \sim 1\text{-}50$ nm) leading to high specific surface areas (SSA) of up to $1315 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ [4], make them interesting materials for the modification of polymer matrix composites. Such modification can lead to improved toughness, compression modulus, Young's modulus and interlaminar shear strength [5-7]. In this work, a servo-hydraulic testing machine has been used in order to carry out controlled impact tests on woven-fabric/epoxy resin CFRP panels, with and without additional CNT reinforcement. In a parallel study, to be reported subsequently, the Mode I & II fracture toughness of the same material has been studied.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Eight layers of plain weave carbon fabric (obtained from Hexforce), stacked in a 0/90 configuration, have been impregnated using a wet lay-up technique with two different epoxy resins obtained from Amroy (Epopox AFLV and Hybtonite; the latter contains a random dispersion of CNTs). The fabric is 3000 filament yarn plain weave (3K-70-P),

and its density is in the range of 1.72 to 1.84 g/cm³. The thicknesses of the panels without and with the additional carbon nanotubes were approximately 1.5 mm and 1.8 mm, respectively. Plain woven-fabric/epoxy resin CFRP panels with and without the additional carbon nanotube reinforcement were manufactured and cut into circular specimens, 140 mm in diameter. The specimens were locked into a specially constructed cage mounted on a servohydraulic fatigue machine to be impacted in low-velocity impact tests where the velocity is controlled and both load and displacement is measured during the test; details of the tests have been provided elsewhere [8]. Three types of test have been carried out, as follows. In the “complete penetration impact test”, the impactor (a 15.7 mm diameter glass sphere) was driven into the two types of specimens at a low, constant velocity of 0.08 mms⁻¹. The second type of test, called a “partial impact test”, involved driving the impactor into the specimen to a certain maximum displacement without completely penetrating the specimen and then withdrawing the impactor at the same velocity. Finally, “multiple impact tests” were also performed, which are similar to partial impact tests, except that in this case the impactor was driven to a certain displacement, withdrawn and then driven to a higher displacement; this was repeated, until full penetration of the specimen occurred.

After some of the partial penetration impact tests (for displacements of 6 mm and 9 mm), cross-sections of the damaged areas were examined. Sections were prepared which were approximately 2 mm from the centre of impact and were examined using optical microscopy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Complete penetration impact tests

Typical load-displacement behaviour for specimens without CNTs and with CNTs is shown in Figure 1. For both types of specimen, the load increases non-linearly to a maximum where macroscopic penetration of the specimen occurs. After this, the load drops and then the increasing displacement punches the impactor through the specimen, with the load decreasing as the impactor displacement increases. The area under the load-displacement plot is, of course, a measure of the energy absorbed during the complete penetration of the specimen (the penetration energy, U_p). The penetration energy for two specimens of each type of sample (without and with CNTs) is shown in Table 1; a 20% to 25% increase in the penetration energy for the panels with carbon nanotubes was found.

Table 1. Absorbed energy for the low-velocity impact tests for complete penetration of the specimens by the indenter.

Specimen type	Energy absorbed, U_p (J)
Without nanotubes	16.1, 15.8
With nanotubes	21.0, 19.4

Figure 1. Load vs displacement for the penetration impact tests. (a) resin without carbon nanotubes; (b) resin without carbon nanotubes; (c) resin with carbon nanotubes; (d) resin with carbon nanotubes

Figure 2. Definition of the impact energy (U_{imp}) and absorbed energy (U_{abs}) for a specimen impacted to a displacement of 10 mm. Note that the energy absorbed in a full-penetration test, (U_p) is the total energy under the curve [8].

Partial impact tests

In the partial impact tests, the impactor is driven into the specimen to a depth which is less than full penetration and then withdrawn. Following Sofocleous et al [8], two related energies can be derived from this test. Firstly, the “impact energy” (U_{imp}) is the work expended up to the maximum displacement (i.e. in Figure 2, up to a displacement of 10 mm); the absorbed energy (U_{abs}) is the energy which is not recovered when the

impactor is withdrawn. The energy for complete penetration (U_p), must be obtained from a separate test, and is, of course, the energy under the load-displacement curve. Load-displacement behaviour during partial impact tests for a displacement of 6 mm are shown in Figure 3 for specimens without and with carbon nanotube additions. For both types of specimens, the load increased non-linearly to a maximum value and the impact energy is given by the area under the load-displacement curve at this point (U_{imp}). On unloading, a hysteresis is seen (as shown schematically in Figure 2) and the energy absorbed is given by the area of the hysteresis loop (U_{abs}). For both types of specimens, the absorbed energy was quite small for a maximum displacement of 6 mm, with little difference between the specimens without and with CNTs. However, the results of similar tests with a maximum displacement of 9 mm (Figure 4) show large differences between the two types of specimens, with both the impact energies and the absorbed energies being larger for the specimens with CNTs.. This is consistent with the higher energy absorption of the specimens with CNTs in the complete penetration impact tests.

Figure 3. Load vs displacement for the partial penetration impact tests for a penetration of 6 mm. (a) resin without carbon nanotubes; (b) resin without carbon nanotubes; (c) resin with carbon nanotubes; (d) resin with carbon nanotubes

Figure 4. Load vs displacement for the partial penetration impact tests of 9 mm. (a) resin without carbon nanotubes; (b) resin without carbon nanotubes; (c) resin with carbon nanotubes; (d) resin with carbon nanotubes

Multiple impact tests

For the multiple impact tests, the resulting load-displacement behaviour for specimens without and with carbon nanotubes are shown in Figures 5(a) and 5(b), respectively. Overall, it can be seen that the shape of the envelope of these curves is very similar to the shape for the complete penetration impact tests shown in Figure 1. Inspection of the load-displacement behaviour for specimens without carbon nanotubes shows, as before, that the load drops away quite steeply after the initial through-thickness penetration of the specimens. For the specimens with CNTs, the load does not fall away as rapidly, with the result that the energy absorption, given by the area under the load-displacement plot, is higher for the panels with CNTs.

Calculating the impact energy and absorbed energy for each displacement is more complicated for the multiple impact tests because the re-loading curves overlap the previous unloading curves. Consequently, in deriving the overall energy absorbed in these tests, the overlapping areas should not be double-counted. Table 2 shows typical cumulative impact energy (U_{imp}) and absorbed energy (U_{abs}) at the various displacements for the panels without and with nanotubes. The results show that, for a given displacement, the impact energies (U_{imp}) are larger for the panel with carbon nanotubes, and the absorbed energies become larger for the specimens with CNTs after the through-thickness penetration of the specimen, which occurred at a displacement of about 7 mm. Of course, both the impact and absorbed energies are equal to the

penetration energy when full penetration of the specimen occurs; as with the single impact tests, the specimens with CNTs absorb more energy for complete penetration of the specimens. Overall, the results for specimens with and without CNTs show that there is about a 20 to 25% increase in the penetration energy for the panels with carbon nanotubes compared to panels without CNTs.

Figure 5 Load vs displacement for the multiple impact test (a) resin without carbon nanotubes; (b) resin with carbon nanotubes

Table 2. Impact (U_{imp}) and absorbed (U_{abs}) energies for the specimens with and without nanotubes for each displacement of the multiple impact tests.

Displacement (mm)	Resin without nanotubes		Resin with nanotubes	
	U_{imp} (J)	U_{abs} (J)	U_{imp} (J)	U_{abs} (J)
2	0.25	0.02	0.32	0.02
4	1.55	0.24	1.86	0.26
6	4.81	1.27	5.32	1.74
7	6.97	4.75	7.25	4.48
8	8.45	6.38	8.79	6.09
9	9.83	7.78	10.51	7.90
10	11.25	9.45	12.12	9.47
12	13.53	12.07	15.42	12.95
18	15.30	15.29	18.80	18.73

Relationship between the impact, absorbed and penetration energies

Martello and colleagues [9] have suggested an empirical relationship between the impact, absorbed and penetration energies measured in drop-weight impact tests. Sofocleous et al [8], applied this approach to controlled impact experiments on woven E-glass/epoxy resin specimens, finding a relationship between the impact, absorbed and penetration energies which is very similar to that of Martello and colleagues, i.e.:

$$\frac{U_{abs}}{U_p} = \left(\frac{U_{imp}}{U_p} \right)^n, \text{ where } n \text{ is in the range } 1.5 \text{ to } 2 \quad (1)$$

This expression has been applied to the results shown in Tables 1 and 2 for both the composites without and with CNTs, and the resulting graph is shown in Figure 6. In the same figure, Eqtn 1 has been plotted using exponents of 1.5 and 2 and it is clear that the results are in agreement with Eqtn 1 for these values of the exponent, n . In terms of agreement with this empirical expression, there is no difference between the specimens without and with CNTs. At present, the underlying reasons why this empirical relationship fits the data so well remain unclear.

Figure 6 Normalised impact and absorbed energies plotted in accordance with Equation (1) for two kinds of specimens: eight-layer woven fabric laminates with and without carbon nanotubes.

Figure 7 Cutting the specimens to be cross sectional damage areas in two directions (a) the specimen without nanotubes (b) the specimen with nanotubes.

Figure 8. Cross-sections of specimens located 2 mm from the centre of impact for specimens impacted to a displacement of 9 mm: (a) specimen without CNTs viewed at cross-section A; (b) specimen without CNTs viewed at cross-section B; (c) specimen with CNTs viewed at cross-section A; (d) specimen with CNTs viewed at cross-section B. A scale marker for 1000 μm is shown at the bottom left of the figure.

Microstructural damage observations

In the microstructural analysis of the impacted specimens, the terms *impact* and *exit* face of the specimens are used here which refer to the faces impacted and exited by the impactor, respectively. Microstructural damage observations were made after partial penetration impact tests with 6 mm and 9 mm displacements. Figure 7 shows the appearance of the exit faces of both specimens, (a) without nanotubes and (b) with nanotubes, for the partial impact tests with 9 mm displacements. The figure also indicates the positions at which cross-sections of the specimens were cut for microscopical examination. For example, in Figure 7(a), “Side A” and “Side B” indicate the position of the cross-sections which were examined under the microscope, and the same is shown for Figure 7(b). As mentioned above, the position of the cross-sections examined were 2 mm from the impact centre. Figure 8 shows sections of two composite specimens, without and with CNTs, both impacted to a displacement of 9

mm. It can be seen that for the specimen without nanotubes (Figures 8(a) and 8(b)) that substantial fracture throughout the thickness of the composite has occurred for this impactor displacement, whereas less damage is evident in the specimen containing a dispersion of CNTs (Figure 8(c) and 8(d)). This is consistent with a higher resistance to impact damage being shown by the specimens additionally reinforced with CNTs after penetration of the specimen.

For displacements below the peak load, i.e. before through-thickness penetration begins, the differences between the specimens without and with CNTs is less obvious. Figure 9 shows similar cross-sections for both types of specimens for an impact displacement of 6 mm (again the cross-sections are at a distance of 2 mm from the impact centre) and only minor damage can be seen near the exit face of both types of specimen.

Figure 9. Cross-sections of specimens located 2 mm from the centre of impact for specimens impacted to a displacement of 6 mm: (a) specimen without nanotubes; (b) specimen with nanotubes.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this paper it has been shown that the absorbed energy during the complete penetration of specimens in a low-velocity controlled impact test increased by approximately 20 to 25% when the polymer matrix contained carbon nanotube additions. Comparison of the cross-sections for specimens with and without CNTs after a partial penetration impact test has shown that more extensive fracture through the thickness of the specimen occurred in the panel without CNT reinforcement for the same displacement. This is in agreement with the CNT-loaded specimens showing a higher resistance to impact penetration, which is reflected in the higher overall energy absorption for complete penetration of the specimens by the impactor. An analysis of the impact test results for the specimens without and with CNTs (in relation to the impact, absorbed and penetration energies) has found the results to be in agreement with an empirical relationship suggested in the literature.

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